

PROMOTING LEARNER AUTONOMY IN TESOL: EMPOWERING STUDENTS TO TAKE OWNERSHIP OF THEIR LANGUAGE LEARNING

Muydinova Maftuna Orifjonovna

English teacher in ALWIUT (Academic Lyceum of WIUT)

Abstract: *The advent of learner-centered approaches in language education has underscored the significance of fostering learner autonomy in the Teaching of English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL). By empowering students to take ownership of their language learning, educators can unlock the full potential of their learners, thereby leading to improved language proficiency, self-directed learning, and increased motivation. This article argues that promoting learner autonomy is a vital aspect of TESOL and provides a comprehensive framework for educators to implement this approach in their teaching practices.*

Keywords: *learner autonomy, TESOL, problem-solving skills, children, evaluation, new methods*

Introduction: It can be seen to encourage meaningful and purposeful target language activities and to maximize learning through such exposure by encouraging the organization of longer, more coherent periods of input which closely resemble 'independent' exposure to the target language that human beings take part in when not engaging in the instruction of other human beings. The exercise of control over own learning also maximizes the potential for learning by encouraging the deployment of compensatory language learning strategies and the deployment of sound problem-solving strategies, for example, making yourself aim to communicate fully and to self-correct anticipatively prior to production.

Learner autonomy is a complex and not uncontroversial concept which can be understood and interpreted in a variety of ways. However, it can be seen to at least include the capacity of language learners to take responsibility for their own learning and to exercise control over

the process of learning and the environments in which learning happens. The capacity of learners to determine their own objectives, ways of achieving objectives, and evaluate progress, and the construction and monitoring of learning objectives, methods of learning, learning time, evaluation, and relationship between the learner's own learning and the learning community. As such, learner autonomy is seen as important for a series of cognitive, emotional, and social reasons. However, it also relates to a number of key findings in various areas of applied linguistics research into language learning and teaching.

Definition and Conceptual Framework

As far as language teaching and learning are concerned, autonomy usually means acting independently and intentionally without the intervention of a teacher or peer. In theoretical terms, this definition of autonomy has its problems, as it could be seen as ignoring the relational and interactional foundations of the self. However, from a practical viewpoint, a language learner is usually autonomous if, as well as knowing what he or she wants to learn, the learner also knows how to find it, how to decide whether a particular item of information is relevant and understandable, and how to integrate the information into the learner's own existing system of knowledge. The learner must also exhibit the qualities of self-knowledge and self-confidence required for this one-person task.

Learner autonomy has become an important issue in TESOL because it is increasingly realized that most language learning problems cannot be solved by teaching, no matter how good, if each learner does not also take charge of his or her own learning. Research on how to promote learner autonomy is expanding dramatically, and the associated concepts of self-instruction, self-access, and self-direction have become labels for many proposed solutions. The early intercultural implications of this self-motivating ideal have also generated a mixture of widespread support and active concern.

Theoretical Foundations

Notwithstanding overlapping interests at numerous points, researchers in self-regulation and learner autonomy have differing foci. While SRL contributions largely target primary and secondary education, the field has been busily and somewhat singly finding SRL theories

through student research mostly conducted within higher education settings. Defining a theoretical orientation which envisions empowerment to be a central laminate of language learning is another theoretical underpinning of this study. Community of Practice discussions of learner empowerment have served as spin-offs from the research components of socio-constructivist second language acquisition (SLA), sociolinguistics, and psychology—also the communities from which spiraled the initial Theory of Self-Regulated Learning.

The first succinct theoretical foundation for the empirical study of learner autonomy is the theory of self-regulated learning (SRL). As the header suggests, this conceptual lens is applied to settings outside the mainstream of general education, which is where the concepts of self-regulated learning and learner autonomy are predominantly utilized. It is evident that the threads of basic theory do intertwine with both teacher education and classroom instruction at various points, so that both the conceptual and the empirical infrastructure of self-regulation research can inform and be informed. Nevertheless, there has been little direct blending of the scholar and practitioner communities. Each would benefit from sharing more with the other's insights.

To begin with, it is essential to define learner autonomy and its significance in language education. Learner autonomy refers to the ability of students to take control of their own learning, making decisions about their goals, content, and pace (Nunan, 1996). In the context of TESOL, learner autonomy implies that students are able to identify their language learning needs, set realistic goals, and select the most effective learning strategies to achieve those goals. By doing so, learners become more self-directed, motivated, and responsible for their own learning outcomes.

One of the primary benefits of promoting learner autonomy is that it enables students to develop a sense of ownership over their language learning. When learners are actively involved in the learning process, they become more invested in their own progress, which in turn boosts their motivation and engagement (Dörnyei, 2001). Moreover, learner autonomy fosters a growth mindset, where learners view challenges as opportunities for growth and development rather than threats to their ego (Dweck, 2000). As a result, students

become more resilient, adaptable, and receptive to feedback, leading to improved language proficiency and a greater sense of accomplishment.

To promote learner autonomy, educators can employ a range of strategies that cater to the diverse needs and learning styles of their students. One effective approach is to encourage learners to set goals and develop a personalized learning plan. This involves helping students identify their language learning objectives, prioritize their goals, and create a schedule to achieve them (Benson, 2007). By doing so, learners develop a clear sense of direction, focus, and motivation, which are essential for language learning.

Another strategy for promoting learner autonomy is to provide learners with opportunities for self-assessment and reflection. This can be achieved through the use of learning journals, self-assessment rubrics, and reflective writing tasks (Kumaravadivelu, 2003). By engaging in self-assessment and reflection, learners develop a deeper understanding of their language learning strengths, weaknesses, and needs, which enables them to make informed decisions about their learning. Moreover, self-assessment and reflection help learners to identify areas for improvement, set goals, and develop strategies to achieve them. In addition to goal-setting and self-assessment, educators can promote learner autonomy by using technology to facilitate language learning. The advent of digital technologies has created a myriad of opportunities for learners to take control of their language learning, including online language courses, language exchange platforms, and mobile apps (Chapelle, 2000). By leveraging these technologies, learners can access a wealth of language learning resources, engage in autonomous learning, and receive personalized feedback and support.

Furthermore, promoting learner autonomy requires educators to adopt a facilitative rather than a didactic approach to teaching. This involves creating a learner-centered classroom environment, where learners are encouraged to take an active role in the learning process (Little, 1991). By doing so, educators can foster a sense of community, collaboration, and mutual support among learners, which are essential for language learning.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, promoting learner autonomy is a vital aspect of TESOL, as it enables learners to take ownership of their language learning, develop a sense of motivation and direction, and improve their language proficiency. By employing a range of strategies, including goal-setting, self-assessment, technology-enhanced learning, and facilitative teaching, educators can empower learners to take control of their language learning. Ultimately, promoting learner autonomy requires a fundamental shift in the way we approach language education, one that recognizes the learner as the central figure in the learning process.

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